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A platform management system that links commuters with shared or service taxis

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ABSTRACT

This paper outlines a management system developed specifically for linking commuters in Beirut, Lebanon, with shared taxis (also known as "service"). In this paper, shared taxis are the ones that have been registered with the Syndicate of Lebanese Taxi Drivers. The objective of the system, which was distinguished by the absence of fixed transportation schedules and pre-defined stops, was to create a comprehensive platform called "Platform to Promote and Optimize Collective Taxi Access (PCT)" that provided commuters with a variety of route options between selected departure and destination points. The route options were selected and categorized based on the preferences of commuters. In Beirut, the findings of the initial prototype were deemed efficient and adequate in terms of unimodal mobility and providing commuters with a customized travel experience.

1. INTRODUCTION

A 15-year civil war transformed Beirut, once renowned as the "Pearl of the Middle East," into a true no-man's land (1975-1990). Parts of the city were demolished, roads were damaged, and train services were halted as a result. Since then, Lebanon has lacked a sustainable and efficient infrastructure and transportation system, which has exacerbated road congestion. Commutes in Lebanon have become a daily misery due to the country's severe traffic congestion. Lack of real efforts to modernize public transportation has also negatively impacted the economy of Lebanon. Access to low-cost collective transportation, such as shared taxis (or "service"), has become essential in this regard (Choueiri et al., 2015). However, the subject of encouraging and enhancing the relationship between commuters and communal transportation in Lebanon remained unsolved. Based on this foundation, the Antonine University in Lebanon initiated a project titled "Platform to Promote and Optimize Access to Collective Taxis," which featured both front-end and back-end systems, in an effort to increase commuters' awareness of collective transportation. The back-end of the platform was developed to optimize and encourage the use of collective transportation. It promoted shared taxis as the primary mode of transportation. This mode of transportation was characterized by the absence of predetermined transit times and stop locations. The project's major objective was to expand the use of shared taxis, notably in Beirut, by making them more accessible to anyone in need of transportation.

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2. RELATED WORK

Several transportation corporations and operators are developing innovative information technologies to make commuters' lives easier. These systems provide commuters with pre-trip information and real-time navigational guidance for transportation networks. Despite the fact that several routing applications are now in use, these systems do not always satisfy the expectations of commuters and are limited by a variety of constraints.

From this vantage point, the authors examined the merits and drawbacks of applications connected to both unimodal and multimodal modes of transportation. Numerous programs, including CIMO (Hassine and Canalda, 2015), TIMIPlan (Garcia et al., 2012), Busfinder (Tsolkas et al., 2012), and MaaS (MCOMM, 2018); (Cole, 2018), have tackled unimodal and multimodal transportation difficulties.

TIMIPlan is an application that addressed both the Unimodal Transportation Problem (UTP) and the Multimodal Transportation Problem (MTP) for a large Spanish company. It expedited the transfer of resources and decreased the amount of time required. It addressed the MTP by combining Linear Programming (LP) with autonomous planning approaches, taking into account the limits imposed by both shared taxis (in terms of working hours) and consumers. To combat UTP, a MOACS (Multi-objective Ant Colony System) strategy was devised and applied, with several adjustments, such as allowing commuters to choose between reducing the number of automobiles and the total cost (Dib et al., 2016); Fiorenzo-Catalano, 2007); and Flórez et al., 2011).

CIMO (Calculateur d'Itinéraires Multimodaux Ordonnés) is a travel planner for the Belfort-Montbéliard region of France. The CTPM, SMTC, SMAU, SNCF, and Illicom networks comprise its transportation network. This repeated combination, employing a dynamic programming technique termed as "Cut, Price, and Share", did solve the MTP (Hassine and Canalda, 2015).

BusFinder is a mobile application designed to make Athens' (Greece) public transit more convenient. Based on a dynamic algorithm, the system provides a map depicting the various bus stops in the neighborhood of the commuter, as well as alternative routes of buses in the network, arrival times (taking into account traffic congestion), and navigation directions. Utilizing the DRO (Dynamic Route Optimization) method, this application processes real-time data from a Fleet Management System (FMS) and an Open Trip Planner (OTP). Overall, the application takes into account two steps: filtering data by deleting any extraneous information based on search queries and ranking results according to commuter preferences (Tsolkas et al., 2012).

MaaS is commonly viewed as a commuter-centric model of transportation that offers an on-demand, real-time platform that incorporates any combination of transport modalities, such as car, bike sharing, and taxis, and covers everything for the commuter, from journey planning to payments. It attempts to break down the barriers between the government transport agency, service providers, and transport operators, and to bring them closer to the customers. Using a single, unified trip planning and payment application, MaaS directs users to the most relevant mobility alternatives in real time (MCOMM, 2018). MaaS offers itself as a subscription-based service that permits commuters to select several forms of transportation for a subscription fee or pay-as-you-go (Cole, 2018). MaaS can provide commuters with flexibility in selecting travel modes, timings, and costs in a city with multiple forms of transportation.

Hedi et al. (2009) and Ayed et al. (2011) offered a hybrid multimodal transportation solution. They used the ACO (Ant Colony Optimization) method to reduce the main memory consumption, resulting in an abstract graph that was a streamlined version of the original graph. The Dijkstra algorithm was then applied within an acceptable amount of time to determine the shortest route.

Mahi et al. (2012) developed a routing algorithm to suggest a novel formulation for a multimodal network. On the Paris (and suburbs) transportation networks, this formulation was tested. Railways, buses, trams, metros, walking, automobile roadways, and bicycle paths were among the means of transportation studied. As optimization criteria, the authors utilized the total duration of the trip, the number of exchanges, and the total amount of time spent walking. Each network was modeled separately as a graph, as the initial step in their modeling procedure.

In addition, Mahi et al. (2012) distinguished between forms of private transportation that provided continuous service and modes of public transportation according to a predetermined timetable. In this way, every submodel was incorporated into a single global model. For example, the pedestrian network was used to shift from one mode to another; to link to the road network, parking lot nodes were utilized. Following network modeling, a modified version of Dijkstra's algorithm was employed to address the problem of shortest paths with several criteria.

Santos et al. (2007) provided three approaches for discovering the k-shortest paths: a route elimination algorithm, a deviation path algorithm based on the work of Eppstein (1998), and a deviation path algorithm with extra processing enhancement. In this regard, Martins and Pascoal (2003) examined a novel version of Yen's algorithm for rating loopless pathways.

3. THE PROPOSED PCT SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

This paper describes a platform that can improve access to shared taxis in Lebanon that are registered with the Syndicate of Lebanese Taxi Drivers. In contrast to community transportation platforms and services offered in industrialized nations, shared taxis in Lebanon lack predetermined stop stations and regulated transit periods. In addition, they differ from shared transportation services, such as Uber and Careem, in that they do not offer reservation-in-advance choices; therefore, the commuter must hunt for or wait for the next available shared taxi that passes through his/her location. The approaches, including our recommended platform, are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. The Comparative table between our approach and various solutions available

	Schedules	Way of moving	Meeting point	Booking Possibility
Collective transport in developed countries	Non-flexible but repetitive	The commuter	Predefined by stops	No
Uber and Careem	Flexible but non-repetitive	The shared taxi	Provided by the commuter	Yes
The project presented in this paper	Non-flexible and non-repetitive	The commuter	Set by the algorithm	No

The five steps of our platform include data collection, graph construction, pre-processing, routing, and rating. Figure 1 depicts the steps of our platform; a detailed explanation of each level follows.

Figure 1. The proposed PCT System architecture

3.1 Data Collection

Regarding the local database, there were eleven tables. These eleven tables were divided into three categories: five tables pertaining to data from Lebanon's geographical map; five tables pertaining to data from platform commuters; and one table pertaining to the algorithm's output. The database is depicted in Figure 2.

We used "Open Street Map" for this purpose, as its data is considered an open source for acquiring geographic information. For this, we downloaded:

- the relational database management system-PostgreSQL;
- the Postgis software, which supports the addition of geographic objects to the PostgreSQL database;
- a file representing the geographical map of Lebanon of type ".OSM";
- the "OSM2Pgrouting" software, which converted the data from this file into tables based on the configuration chosen.

OSM_Nodes, OSM_WAY_TYPES, OSM_WAY_CLASSES, WAYS, and WAYS_VERTICES_PGR were the five tables relating to the geographical map of Lebanon. "weight_s" and "reverse_weight_s" were added to the Ways table to reflect the time required for a pedestrian to cross the road from the starting location to the destination point.

Figure 2. The database diagram

The five tables pertaining to commuters were likewise divided into two categories: two tables pertaining to the commuter, whether a driver or a commuter (commuters, requirements), and three tables pertaining to the driver alone (CARS, PATHS and MAP). These five tables were filled in by the platform's Front-End. In other words, the front-end portion of the platform was utilized to determine the commuter's attributes (personal information, location, requirements, vehicles, and paths).

Finally, a representative table of the routing algorithm's results (Results) was created. This table was loaded by the server-side component. It included the date of the routing request, the commuter's identification number, the commuter's initial location, and the commuter's ultimate destination. It also contained all of the nodes and arcs used to reach M-meeting-points and n-shared taxi-destinations while satisfying the commuter's request and the algorithm's constraints. In addition, it included the time required for commuters and shared taxis to reach the meeting locations, as well as the total duration.

3.2 Graph Creation

Following the acquisition of data, particularly those associated with the geographical map, the creation of the graph was initiated. The items of the Ways table created the arcs, whilst the elements of the Ways_Vertices_PGR table formed the nodes, with each Ways item connecting two Ways_Vertices_PGR elements.

3.3 Pre-processing

This step preceded the phase of the algorithm. Therefore, it must provide the essential environment for algorithm execution. It pertains to:

- Determining the commuter's current location and desired final destination from the "requirements" table.
- Examining the commuter's position on the graph and determining if a virtual node and virtual arcs should be created for him or whether a node and an arc adequately define his position.
- Locating the target node, validating his position, and choosing whether a virtual node and virtual arcs should be created for him.
- Locating all available shared taxis in the vicinity of the commuter, including their positions and trajectories.
- Creating subgraphs for each shared taxi and commuter to reduce the number of nodes and arcs in the initial graph in order to facilitate the operation of the routing algorithm.

Figure 3 displays the procedure used. Noteworthy is that, in the case of shared taxis, the corresponding information, such as location, was regarded if the taxi was within a 1 km square, with the commuter at its center.

In an effort to reduce the number of nodes and arcs in the initial graph, subgraphs were constructed following data extraction. Our proposed technique utilized the Yen algorithm to discover the 100 shortest paths between the commuter's current position and his final destination in order to construct the subgraphs relating to him. The shared taxis were then represented by a subgraph consisting of a succession of arcs representing their current locations and final destination.

3.4 Routing

Our suggested algorithm used computation, analysis, and decision-making techniques to present the location points where the commuter and shared taxis intersected, as well as the respective travel times. Noteworthy is that each location point must adhere to the constraint that the commuter's arrival time at the location point must be smaller than that of the shared taxi.

Figure 3. Pre-processing steps

Figure 4. Routing block diagram

Our proposed approach pooled numerous shared taxis within the same intersecting nodes, hence eliminating redundancy. Each location point was also assigned a priority. Priority varied based on whether the shared cab traveled directly through the commuter's neighborhood, passed close to the commuter's destination, or neither of these.

Figure 4 displays the methods performed to identify M-meeting points and present commuters with a range of options.

In addition, each shared taxi was given a priority. The shared taxis were categorized as those that traveled directly through the nodes of the commuter's destination, those that traveled through the nodes around the nodes of the commuter's destination, or those that did not travel through the nodes of the commuter's destination.

Our proposed method started by finding the arcs and nodes connecting a commuter to a shared taxi. Then, the commuter subparagraph and the shared taxi subparagraph were compared. If the arcs or nodes of the subgraphs matched, the mutual arc or node was added to the database of the shared taxi. Then, the Dijkstra algorithm was used to compute the time required to reach the intersecting points. The computed time represented the time required by the algorithm for the commuter/shared taxi to go from the current node to the meeting location. The commuters' and the shared taxi's arrival times at each meeting location were then calculated and examined. If the commuter's arrival time at the node was less than the shared taxi's arrival time, the node was deemed a valid meeting location and subsequently included in the primary findings.

A procedure of redundancy removal was implemented for secondary results. The initial sorting of the primary data collected for each shared taxi was based on the commuters' arrival times at the meeting locations. Then, an investigation was conducted of the numerous nodes and arcs required for the commuter to reach the meeting locations. If a commuter could reach the same shared taxi from two separate locations, and assuming that path A was shorter than path B, then path B was eliminated and path A's priority was adjusted accordingly.

After receiving the secondary results, a comparison of shared taxis was undertaken. In other words, if a commuter at a certain meeting location had the option to select a group of shared taxis with the same priority ranking, then these shared taxis were grouped together. This process led to the creation, examination, and archiving of the final findings.

3.5 Ranking

The purpose of this phase was to rate the findings collected during the routing phase. Priority was allocated to each ranking, which varied by mode of transportation.

In the case of unimodal transportation, data from shared taxis traveling straight to the destination or via surrounding nodes were taken into account. They were ranked according to the possibility of encountering as many shared taxis as feasible and the commuter's arrival time at the meeting location.

In the case of multimodal transportation, a post-processing step was performed to provide the commuter with the required trip information, from the first meeting point with the first shared taxi to the second meeting point with the second shared taxi, and so on, until the commuter reached his final destination.

4. RESULTS

The results of our suggested algorithm were categorized by mode of transportation and the mode of arrival at the final destination. The outcomes were divided into three groups: direct route arrivals (A_{direct}), two-mode arrivals (A_{2mode}), and one-mode two-stage arrivals (A_{2stage}). In the first group, only shared taxis that traveled through the commuter's destination nodes were evaluated (a direct route arrival). The results were rated in ascending order based on the commuter's arrival time at the meeting point and in a decreasing order of priority; the priority was established based on the commuter's likelihood of finding a shared taxi.

The total duration of the completed journey was determined using equation (1). This duration was given by:

$$\mathbf{duration}_{\text{total}} = \mathbf{time}_{\text{commuter}} + \mathbf{time}_{\text{waiting}} + \mathbf{time}_{\text{trip}} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{time}_{\text{commuter}}$ represented the commuter's maximum travel time to the meeting location, $\mathbf{time}_{\text{waiting}}$ referred to the amount of time a commuter spends waiting for a shared taxi, and $\mathbf{time}_{\text{trip}}$ denoted the required time duration between the meeting point and the final destination.

The second category, known as "a two-mode arrival," corresponded to foot travel and the use of a shared taxi. Consideration was given to the findings received from shared taxis that did not travel through the destination but did pass through a neighboring node. The findings were ranked in ascending order by the commuter's arrival time at the meeting location and in descending order according to the importance of reaching the final destination. Equation (2) was then utilized to determine the total duration of the journey.

$$\mathbf{duration}_{\text{total}} = \mathbf{time}_{\text{commuter}} + \mathbf{time}_{\text{waiting}} + \mathbf{time}_{\text{trip}} + \mathbf{time}_{\text{walking}} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{time}_{\text{commuter}}$ represented the average time it took the commuter to reach the meeting point, $\mathbf{time}_{\text{waiting}}$ denoted the time the commuter spent waiting for the shared taxi, $\mathbf{time}_{\text{trip}}$ denoted the time taken by the commuter to travel from the meeting point to the nearest neighboring node. Furthermore, $\mathbf{time}_{\text{walking}}$ denoted the duration of travel till the final destination.

The third group, "one-mode two-stage arrival," corresponded to a trip made using two shared taxis. In this study, data acquired from shared taxis that did not pass through or travel near the commuter's final destination were disregarded.

5. EXPERIMENTATION

This section describes the algorithm's implementation and the ensuing consequences. Open Street Map was utilized in conjunction with PostgreSQL and PostGIS to obtain a geographical map of Beirut (see Figure 5). "pgRouting" was used to calculate the k-shortest pathways. As an alternative to the front-end services, QGIS was used to graphically display the results of the back-end system.

Figure 5. Geographical map of Beirut – Lebanon

The experimental map of Beirut was a network of 1760 arcs and 1347 nodes, with the lines representing the arcs and the points representing the nodes (see Figure 6). We used the QGIS software to visualize this graph. The tracks or trajectories of fifteen shared taxis were analyzed and assigned the numbers 1001 to 1015. To build the trajectories, sites on the geographical map were identified and the shortest routes between them were then computed.

Figure 6. Constructed graph of Beirut – Lebanon

Figures 7 and 8 exhibit two-path examples for two distinct shared taxis, # 1001 and # 1002, with red circles representing current shared taxi positions, yellow squares representing the meeting points, and black lines on arcs representing the paths

Figure 7. An example showing a shared taxi's path

Figure 8. An example showing another shared taxi's path

Each test considered various settings for the commuter's location, destination, number of shared taxis, maximum distance between the destination and neighboring nodes, and number of k-shortest paths. The ideal number of shortest paths to use while building the commuter subgraph was determined through a series of tests.

As an example, let us consider commuter 10005. This commuter is now located at (35.47936097, 33.89542295) and is on his way to his ultimate destination (35.48869691, 33.89911935). This commuter was not connected to any nodes or arcs. Therefore, a virtual node with the ID 999001 and virtual arcs were necessary. Likewise, this commuter's eventual destination was neither constrained by a node nor an arc. Therefore, a virtual node and virtual arcs were required to connect the destination nodes to the final destination.

As illustrated in Figure 9, the current location of the commuter is depicted in red (or a circle), while the destination is depicted in blue (or Rectangle). The virtual arcs are illustrated in yellow (or Squares). This figure also depicts the 100 shortest routes between the commuter's current location and the destination, as well as the locations of the drivers.

Figure 9. Commuter #10005 (his location and destination)

The values of the variables "destinationInTrajectory" and "destinationNearTrajectory", as well as the corresponding priority, are displayed in Table 2. If "destinationInTrajectory" was true, the shared taxi was travelling through the commuter's final destination. Similarly, if the "destinationNearTrajectory" attribute was true, it indicated that the shared taxi was travelling through the commuter's destination area, with nodes located 200 meters away.

Table 2. Results concerning the shared taxis corresponding to commuter #10005

The visible drivers	The number of intersecting arcs	The number of intersecting nodes	The value of the InTrajectory destination variable	The value of the NearTrajectory destination variable	The driver's priority
1001	23	19	False	False	0
1002	16	15	False	False	0
1003	65	63	True	True	100
1004	27	23	False	False	0
1005	22	20	False	True	50
1006	42	37	True	True	100
1007	22	20	False	True	50
1008	47	51	False	True	50
1010	2	1	False	False	0
1011	0	0	False	False	0
1012	22	20	False	True	50
1013	5	4	False	False	0
1014	20	18	True	True	100
1015	21	38	False	False	0

The initial phase of the algorithm (finding the primary meeting points) identified fifteen primary or valid meeting points. Following grouping and reduction of redundancy, the total number of meeting points decreased to seven. The results are summarized in Table 3. The IDs "1, 2, 3" for Shared taxi #1006 were added to Table 4's results, while the IDs "4, 5, 6" for Shared taxi #1008 were added to Table 5's results.

Table 3. The meeting points allocated to commuter #10005

The result's ID	The meeting point	The intersecting shared taxis	Priority of the result
1	Node 635	Driver #1006	100
2	Node 531	Driver #1006	102
3	Node 738	Driver #1006	101
4	Node 90	Driver #1008	51
5	Node 379	Driver #1008	50
6	Node 1092	Driver #1008	51
7	Node 635	Driver #1001 or Driver #1004 or Driver #1010	2

Table 4. An example of recording the results in the "Adirect" table

The attributes	Their values	The attributes	Their values
psg_id	10005	psg_time	00:36
source_x	35.47936097	meeting_drivers	1006
source_y	33.89542295	meeting_times	01:25
destination_x	35.48869691	directly	TRUE
destination_y	33.89911935	travel_time1	03:46
path_nb	1	hop2	0
nodes	999001,635	node_far	0
edges	999001,-1	psg_time2	0
hop1	635	total_time	05:11
Comments	Choice #1: Commuter #10005, walk 00:36 minutes to point 635. A shared taxi will meet you there. Shared taxi #1006 will arrive in 01:25 minutes to take you to your destination. The overall duration of your trip is 05:11 minutes.		

Table 5. Results corresponding to the "A2mode"

The attributes	Their values	The attributes	Their values
psg_id	10005	psg_time	00:30
source_x	35.47936097	meeting_drivers	1008
source_y	33.89542295	meeting_times	02:40
destination_x	35.48869691	directly	False
destination_y	33.89911935	travel_time1	02:07
path_nb	4	hop2	621
nodes	999001,531,90	node_far	186
edges	999003,705,-1	psg_time2	02:13
hop1	90	total_time	07:00
Comments	Choice #4: Commuter #10005, walk 01:30 minutes to point 90. A shared taxi will meet you there. Shared taxi #1008 will arrive in 02:40 minutes to take you to 621, a nearby location to your final destination. From there, walk 186 meters to your destination; it takes roughly 02:13 minutes. The overall duration of your trip is 07:00 minutes.		

The drivers' and commuters' perspectives during the preprocessing step were eliminated after the results were determined. If m was 100, then there were no drivers in the vicinity of the commuter's destination.

6. CONCLUSION

The fast development of digital technology has rendered no industry immune to its consequences. Businesses may contact millions of individuals simultaneously using the web platform. Regarding the ride-hailing industry, the market is currently dominated by it. Those participating in the taxi industry are cognizant of the benefits of investing in the industry. Popularity of the taxi industry can be attributed to the ease of online taxi booking and the chance to enjoy a hassle-free trip.

Regarding shared taxi applications, we believe that the shared taxi app described in this paper will, as time progresses and additional improvements are made, meet all of the commuters' criteria, given that it ensures quality and offers a fantastic commuter experience. Certainly, shared taxi drivers in Lebanon and elsewhere have difficulty communicating with commuters since they cannot track their positions. Using our shared taxi app, the commuter may now connect with the driver with a single tap on his or her cellphone screen, thereby resolving this issue. In addition, our shared taxi software ensures that fewer errors occur and that the commuter-shared taxi driver interface is completed on time. In addition, the app has safety elements, such as displaying the license plate and car model, to guarantee that commuters get into the right vehicle.

6.1 Study Limitations

Given that there are thousands of illegal shared taxis that are wandering the streets of Lebanon in general and Beirut in particular, it is possible that our App may not accurately represent the shared taxis in operation in Lebanon. In this study, only shared taxis that are registered with the Syndicate of Lebanese Taxi Drivers were included.

Because validation is an ongoing process, the authors are conducting more research to determine the most effective strategy for using our App to check its validity on a large scale with respect to future unimodal and multimodal transportation.

6.2 Future Possibilities

In terms of the lack of credible and valid methods for obtaining data on the perceptions of shared taxi drivers in Lebanon, the current study has filled in certain gaps in the literature. Certainly, it is the first of its kind in Lebanon. As with anything novel, there are entry obstacles. It is essential to recognize and deal with the reality of the road ahead. Some obstacles include:

- PCT is primarily intended for urban environments. Due to the illegal shared taxis that are wandering the streets of Lebanon's suburbs and rural areas, PCT may not function well there. This means that residents of these areas will require alternative modes of transport.
- PCT is intended to be used via a mobile application. It is feasible that a commuter portal for booking trips on a computer may become available, but the premise of PCT is that transportation access is portable and on-demand. Not everyone will have access to or desire to arrange vacations using mobile devices.
- Transportation agencies function autonomously. If transportation systems continue to function in silos, coordination of services for commuters across service areas will grow more challenging. Commuters will gain the most from multimodal transportation if transit agencies collaborate about infrastructure and pooled resources.

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